

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Dismantling methods and protocols.

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Executive Summary

ECOBULK aims at implementing a new economy model for composite products in automotive, furniture and building component industrial sectors.

This goal requires a complete value chain revision. The following steps must be reviewed: design, production, distribution and collection, business models, users and stakeholder's platform, and, finally, management of waste streams.

At the end of life of circular designed products, new more homogeneous waste streams will allow for more uniform recovered materials to be fed back into the production line. After having studied the circular economy model, waste sorting and characterization technologies as well as material conditioning technologies, its integration as raw materials in production lines, it is time to standardize waste streams managements.

While validating advanced solutions for collection, sorting and pre-treatments in a new circular model, protocols for disassembling and dismantling these waste streams have been developed. These protocols consider three scenarios in timeline: the State of Art after ECOBULK; in five years' time and in ten years' time.

These protocols aim to guarantee an appropriate identification and characterization of incoming wastes and selection of recovered materials after sorting treatment and strengthen this link within chain value ECOBULK's working on at least on 65% of raw materials.

Advanced solutions for collection, sorting and pre-treatments innovations from TOMRA and AIMPLAS deliverables (D5.3 Solutions for the final sorting of Bulky Waste and D5.4 Solutions of the final sorting of End-of-Life Vehicle Shredder Light Fraction) have allowed an increase of more than 5% the recyclable materials that could be used in the EcoBulk's products from the current ELVs and urban bulky wastes.

This deliverable shows a description of the dismantling and disassembly methods for each product, with a different approach to ensure:

- a) avoiding harm to existing (post-) shredder technologies
- b) remaining compliant to 95% vehicle recycling and 65% of the other two sectors addressed
- c) and capturing potential valuable material content.

Therefore, this deliverable contains the criteria and methodology to optimize these protocols, together with all ECOBULK's developments until now.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Dismantling methods and protocols.....	1
Executive Summary	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	6
TABLE OF FIGURES	8
1. Introduction.....	11
1.1. Description of the document and pursue.....	12
1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable.....	13
2. Dismantling methods in a circular economy model framework.....	17
2.1. Study case 1 Automotive.....	19
Present situation	19
Dismantling tasks developed in Case 1. Automotive industry	20
Conclusions	34
Evaluation of performance indicators.....	35
Case 1 Results	37
2.2. Study case 2 Furniture	44
Present situation	44
Evaluation of performance indicators:.....	45
Case 2 Results	46
2.3. Study case 3 Building components.....	50
Present situation	50
Evaluation of performance indicators.....	51

Case 3 Results	52
3. Dismantling Protocols.....	54
3.1. Automotive protocol.....	55
3.2. Furniture protocol	69
Description.....	70
3.3. Construction protocol	73
Description.....	74
4. Conclusions and recommendations	77
4.2. Automotive plastic trends.....	80
4.3. New strategies to implement	83
4.4. Automotive sector conclusions	86
4.5. Furniture sector conclusions.....	89
4.6. Construction sector conclusions.....	91
5. References.....	93
5.2. References from ECOBULK team previous works	94

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. WP & Tasks that feed D5.2.....	14
Figure 2. WP & Tasks fed by D5.2.....	16
Figure 3. Waste streams management options.....	18
Figure 4. Automotive study cases.....	19
Figure 5. Timeline extension.....	19
Figure 6. Automotive sector present situation summary.....	21
Figure 7. Quality of recyclate moulding compound.....	28
Figure 8. Dismantling time forecast.....	29
Figure 9. Dismantling results.....	29
Figure 10. Most valuable item.....	30
Figure 11. Hazardous items.....	30
Figure 12. Summary of plastics found & metals not recovered automatically.	30
Figure 13. Summary of metals in very small quantities.....	30
Figure 14. Summary items out of ECOBULK's scope.....	30
Figure 15. Mandatory parts to be removed.....	31
Figure 16. Automated removing of parts.....	31
Figure 17. Remaining parts.....	31
Figure 18. Most valuable parts at present.....	32
Figure 19. Summary of parts to work on.....	32
Figure 20. Present ELV revenues.....	33
Figure 21. Percentage of revenues.....	33
Figure 22. Summary of case1 scope.....	35
Figure 23. Questionnaire concept.....	36
Figure 24. Distributed questionnaire.....	37

Figure 25. Microcab analysis.....	37
Figure 26. Electric vehicles analysis.....	38
Figure 27. Maier analysis.	39
Figure 28. Conventional vehicles analysis.	40
Figure 29. Conventional vehicles analysis.	40
Figure 30. Conventional vehicles analysis.	41
Figure 31. Conventional vehicles analysis.	42
Figure 32. Conventional vehicles analysis.	42
Figure 33. Summary of Demo 2.....	45
Figure 34. Timeline extension.....	45
Figure 35. Cosmob and MorettiCompact analysis.	46
Figure 36. Furniture analysis.	47
Figure 37. Furniture analysis.	47
Figure 38. Furniture analysis.	48
Figure 39. Furniture analysis.	48
Figure 40. Furniture analysis.	49
Figure 41. Summary of Demo 3.....	51
Figure 42. Timeline.....	51
Figure 43. Conenor analysis.	52
Figure 44. Building component analysis.....	53
Figure 45. Recycling phases demo 1.....	55
Figure 46. Fascia – Central Console. Commercial version (left) and ECOBULK prototype (right).....	64
Figure 47. ECOBULK Fascia. Front Side (Aesthetic).....	65
Figure 48. ECOBULK Fascia. Back Side (Structural).....	65
Figure 49. ECOBULK Fascia. Video Display Screen Assembly.....	65
Figure 50. ECOBULK Fascia. Air Conditioning Vents Assembly.....	65

Figure 51. Step #1. Fascia+ Air Conditioning Vents+ Dashboard Lower Trim	66
Figure 52. Step #2. Dashboard Lower Trim.....	66
Figure 53. Step #3. Audio System Display+Frame	66
Figure 54. Step #4. Electrical+Electronic Devices.....	66
Figure 55. Case 1 within Ecobulk concept.....	67
Figure 56. Shredding process.....	67
Figure 57. Shredding process visualisation.....	68
Figure 58. Recycling phases demo 2.....	69
Figure 59. New pieces of furniture to be manufactured.....	72
Figure 60. Recycling phases demo 3.....	73
Figure 61. New building components to manufacture.....	76
Figure 62. Strategies to implement.....	85

1. Introduction

During the last decades, waste generation has become a serious problem for our highly industrialised societies. "Ensuring the sustainable management of natural resources and wastes" is one of the four priority areas, which includes the development of a 'Thematic Strategy on Waste Recycling' and initiatives in the field of waste prevention, notably proposals on European Community waste prevention targets.

The proposed strategy on waste management includes a hierarchy of options in which primary emphasis is laid on waste prevention, followed by promotion of recovery (recycling, re-use and energy recovery) and lastly by optimisation of final disposal methods.

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

This document overviews, optimises and validates the strategies and technologies for collection and material recovery (wood, plastics and fibres from bulky products -furniture, building panels and vehicle parts-) for (re-) manufacturing.

The specific objective is producing final guidelines for disassembly and dismantling methods for the products developed in the WP4. That for, established dismantling and disassembly methods description for each ECOBULK's product will address these three goals:

- a) avoid harm to existing (post-) shredder technologies
- b) to remain compliant to 95% vehicle recycling and 65% of the other two sectors addressed
- c) capture potential valuable material content.

Current recycling systems for ELV's are designed to valorise the metallic content. Looking for an optimal commitment of these goals, in this task, a modern vehicle has been dismantled manually and analysed on their material content and dismantling/recycling behaviour (timing, value, etc). Given the ongoing surge in non-metallic, low value and complex materials in the vehicle (and future ELV) in the vehicle body, components and structure has contributed to channel the efforts towards ECOBULK's objectives.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

This deliverable is included in WP5, and more specifically, within the task 5.2, Dismantling methods for the circular designed products. This task main objective is to develop proper dismantling and disassembly methods developed in WP2 for the automobile and bulky products (from furniture and building sectors) at their EoL will be validated from a waste manager perspective.

This way, EoL waste management expertise have validated the recovery of materials for (re-)manufacturing through the use of separate streams which will be eased due to the design of the products.

This task starts at M18 and finished at M36. Therefore, this deliverable D5.2, published on M36, is fed from many previous tasks already completed in ECOBULK project.

More specifically, this task has been supported by WP2 on new Circular Design, WP3 on DEMOs sites, WP6 on identifying and labelling components, WP7 on cost-benefit analysis, and WP8 on standardisation strategies.

A summary of this is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. WP & Tasks that feed D5.2.

At the same time, some tasks and deliverables have been worked simultaneously with Task 5.2; and other tasks and deliverables will be supported by it. These methods will be tested on the manufactured products in WP4.

These methods in conjunction with the database software in WP6 will allow for identifying salvable components from different car models, furniture and building components products, thus guiding the dismantling process.

Environmental and legal requirements will be considered on WP7; and on WP8 these protocols will be considered as part of the exploitation plan.

A summary of this is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. WP & Tasks fed by D5.2.

2. Dismantling methods in a circular economy model framework

Throughout its evolution and diversification, our industrial economy has hardly moved beyond one fundamental characteristic established in the early days of industrialisation: a linear model of resource consumption that follows a 'take-make-dispose' pattern.

Companies harvest and extract materials, use them to manufacture a product, and sell the product to a consumer—who then discards it when it no longer serves its purpose.

A circular economy is an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design. It replaces the 'end-of-life' concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, which impair reuse, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems, and, within this, business models.

This study is focused on looking for opportunities to change waste streams into new raw materials. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Waste streams management options¹.

¹ Ellen-MacArthur-Foundation-Towards-the-Circular-Economy

Dismantling tasks developed in Case 1. Automotive industry

Post-consumer plastics waste or materials occurs as soon as the product or the engineering system (appliance, vehicle, etc.) of which it forms a part has reached the end of its life cycle and has to be disposed of. The injection moulded part and hence the material of which it is made is then aged (weathered and mechanically or thermally stressed), soiled, contaminated with operating fluids, as a function of the purpose it has served, and may have been permanently modified by the user, so that it is no longer identical with the starting component or material.

Post-consumer plastic waste is generally disposed of in an indiscriminate fashion today, as part of the used product. The recycling of used materials, which constitutes the target generally involves the parts being dismantled, identified and sorted, compacted for transport, prepared, homogenised, compounded and also marketed prior to re-use. The material cycle depicted also a highly complex quality cycle. It can be readily seen that each customer up to the final consumer is simultaneously a supplier and hence is not also someone who generates quality. Now that it has been seen that the material recycling of post-consumer waste is technically feasible in a large number of cases, economic observations are being included in the recycling studies carried out.

On the basis of these economic observations, it is possible to estimate the cost of a series of the individual operations. As yet, however, it is too early to draw up balance sheets.

Figure 6. Automotive sector present situation summary.

Single-sort plastics

Used material correctly sorted into individual types will be the first requirement that raw material manufacturers impose to those who are obliged to take back plastics in future or on the third parties that they commission to do this work. Only if this requirement is fulfilled can mechanical recycling of the used material be attempted with any hope of success. This doubtless constitutes a particularly fundamental requirement and one that will scarcely be possible to fulfil in a large number of cases.

The individual used material fractions must be clearly defined if they are to be fed into the recycling processes that are available so far. Under certain conditions, this type of definition may also specify the admissibility of contamination with other polymers (foreign polymers), providing that the stipulated levels are not exceeded.

Identification and recognition

The most important prerequisite for obtaining single-sort fractions is the reliable recognition of the plastic involved or of its principal component, which needs to be defined. This calls for two criteria, firstly, a recognition method and, secondly, a recognition characteristic or identification mark. Dismantling by hand on the basis of dismantling manuals is not sufficient and can only be accepted for a transitional period.

Compacting for transport

If the identification of the plastic and hence the quality of the dismantled post-consumer waste has been ensured, it is necessary to shred the material and to compact it for the journey from the dismantling plant to the recycler (transport compaction) in order to reduce the transport costs. Sorting errors can scarcely be rectified at this stage, or can only be rectified at great expense. The shredded material that is to be transported thus constitutes a quality-assured product for future recycling material loops.

Preparation

The preparation of production or post-consumer waste serves to ensure that the thermoplastic is recovered with an optimum level of purity and in the geometry that is required for the plasticising operations. The resultant product is designated “defined regrind”. Typical preparation operations include grinding and air separation, washing and drying, ply separation, metal elimination, density separation and decontamination. Which of the above operations, or additional methods, should be used, either in isolation or in combination with others, will depend on the nature of the recycling problem on hand.

Paint removal: A large number of plastic moulded parts are painted for aesthetic reasons and/or to provide protection against weathering. In many cases, the paint is not compatible with the coated thermoplastic. Depending on the nature of the thermoplastic, therefore, it is possible for the paint to have a notch effect when it is worked into the material and thus lower the notched impact strength of the thermoplastic, or even damage it. A

mechanical process has been developed for the removal of paint from moulded parts. This permits quantitative separation and removal of the paint and thus ensures optimum conditions for the mechanical recycling of the thermoplastic that has initially protected by the paint.

Metallisation: as with painting, the metal coating of plastics serves both to enhance the appearance of plastics moulding and to provide protection against weathering. The chief variant is galvanochemical coating using ABS or ABS+PC which gives the thermoplastic a metal look (Chromium-plating). In addition, thermoplastics can be coated with aluminium by means of sputtering or the PVD process. Depending on the geometry of the moulded part and the resultant surface/volume ratio, it is possible to achieve metal components of up to 20% through electroplating. A cold grinding process has been developed for the removal of the metal component. This exploits the dissimilar coefficient of thermal expansion of the two components. Employing this process, it is possible to reduce the metal component in pure regrind to $\leq 0.5\%$. The subsequent “dilution” with virgin material in a ratio of 80/20 then gives a recycle with a metal component of approximately 0.1%.

Colouring: The colouring of recycled materials represents an extraordinarily difficult problem. It goes without saying that such a heterogeneous mixture of parts and materials can only give black pigmented regrind even after successful reprocessing in respect of mechanical, thermal and processing properties.

Machinery requirements

The injection moulder will not normally encounter any particular problems when reprocessing plastics (regrinds). A plastic that has undergone preparation in the form of compounding will be available in the form of granulates. It must, however, be borne in mind that regrind has been subject to two additional processing steps involving thermal stressing (initial processing and compounding). The degradation that inevitably occurs is generally reflected in changed flow behaviour. The breakdown of the molecular chain (lower molecular mass and broader molecular mass distribution) leads to an increase in the flowability by comparison to the original material, which, in turn, affects the process parameters. The cavity can thus be filled more rapidly, thereby improving the pressure propagation inside the cavity during the compression and holding pressure phase. This makes the parts heavier and bigger. When regrind or mixtures of regrind and virgin material are processed, it is thus not possible to assume a constant product. Considerably wider tolerances will have to be accepted, at the very least. Machines with good process monitoring facilities or process control systems should thus be employed for the production of quality mouldings.

Over and above this, there is a series of other requirements that need to be placed on the machine in order to permit the following objectives to be met: gentle melting, low residence time, good homogenisation, acceptance of mixed plastic feedstocks, acceptance of a non-uniform granulate feedstock or mixed granulate feedstock, and acceptance of feedstock with additives.

Quality assurance in recycled plastics

Quality of moulded parts implies the suitability of a part for its intended purpose, i.e. its serviceability. However, in a large number of plastics applications, aesthetic, optical quality and processability also play a role. This, however, is not enough to secure the quality of the moulded parts. Even if high-quality raw material is used, a design or a form of processing that is not suitably tailored to plastics can lead to moulded parts which fail to meet up the specifications in terms of their aesthetic, optical and technical quality.

Waste has to be cleaned and have foreign materials removed from it. If possible, it should be separated into individual types or grades. The waste must then be ground. The grind, together with any additives that may be incorporated for post-stabilisation is processed into a moulding feedstock by means of compounding once again.

Different quality assurance and quality inspection measures will be required for the stages involved in the creation of the moulding compound, as a function of the particular point of departure (raw material or waste). The main difficulty encountered in the production of recyclate lies in the starting product “waste”. It is possible to draw a distinction between four different types of waste, as a function of its origin.

Unsorted waste, such as waste from shredder plants. This is generally contaminated with foreign materials that either cannot be removed or can only be removed at great expense. The different types of plastic contained in the waste will not generally be compatible. The logistics problems are least serious with this type of waste.

Unsorted, non-contaminated waste.

This can generally be cleaned more easily. The compatibility of the different sorts of plastics must be checked in each individual case. Present-day assemblies are frequently already made of types of plastic that are compatible with each other when reprocessed. Logistic problems are caused by the fact that the articles have to be taken to collection points or to the producer's and then dismantled there.

Single-type plastics waste.

This does not generally cause any difficulties in respect of compatibility. Care must, however, be taken to ensure that no "toxic waste", such as additives that have been banned in the meantime, are brought with the waste.

Single-grade plastic waste.

This generally offers the most favourable prospects for reprocessing. There are not usually any problems with cleanliness or compatibility. A higher logistics outlay is necessary. However, since products that have been manufactured at only one production plant, or in just a few locations, can occur as post-consumer waste anywhere in the world and need to be collected again.

In line with the four types of plastic waste, it is also possible to divide the recycled bulk made from these different types into four quality grades. See Figure 7

Recyclate Quality grades	Type of plastic waste	Serviceability	Aesthetic/Optical quality	Processability
A	Single-grade	Like virgin material, reduced dynamic stressability	Like virgin material, if coloured other-wise rather poor	Like virgin material, Frequently with greater flowability
B	Single type (sorted)	For reduced requirements	Good surface colour: only dark shades	Reduced processing range, greater
C	Unsorted non-contaminated	For very low – level requirements	Very poor	Very poor, compression moulding
D	Unsorted contaminated	Not generally suitable for any application	Very poor	Very poor, compression moulding

Figure 7. Quality of recyclate moulding compound.

One task of this study case was to dismantle manually a modern vehicle and analyse it on its material content and dismantling/ recycling behaviour (timing, value, etc).

Following link leads to a summary of this task:

https://youtu.be/Z_y4S8W7P8U

A summary of results is shown below.

60"	Hazardous waste: Battery, Diesel oil, Oils, Water, filters and gear oil	Lead battery, fluids and filters	Worker 1
30"	Wheels and tires extraction	Tires and rubber	Worker 2
60"	Front and rear bumpers, mudguard	Valuable plastics	Worker 2
60"	Engine	Metals	Worker 1
30"	Radiator fan, nozzles and tanks	Plastics	Worker 1
30"	Seats	Fabrics and iron	Worker 3
30"	Instrument panel- dashboard	Valuable plastics	Worker 3
30"	Door panel	Valuable plastics	Worker 3
30"	Roof	Fabrics	Worker 3
30"	Electrical wiring	PVC and copper	Worker 1 and worker 2
6h 30min			

Figure 8. Dismantling time forecast.

Dismantling task	Time run	Main content	kg	%	Value
Hazardous waste: Battery, Diesel oil, Oils, Water, filters and gear oil	90"	Lead battery, fluids and filters	15	1,44%	10,50 €
		Oil, gear oil, water, fuel	23	2,21%	- 16,10 €
		Filters	10	0,96%	- 7,00 €
Wheels and tires extraction	65"	Tires	60	5,77%	12,00 €
		Rubber	32	3,08%	- 40,00 €
Front and rear bumpers, mudguard	30"	PPE	42	4,04%	12,60 €
Radiator fan, nozzles and tanks	95"	PA	12	1,15%	3,60 €
Seats	45"	ABS	1	0,10%	0,30 €
Instrument panel- dashboard	100"	PP	3	0,29%	0,90 €
Door panel	75"	PP	5	0,48%	1,50 €
Roof	30"	PP/ABS	6	0,57%	1,80 €
Electrical wiring	60"	PVC and copper	10	0,96%	16,00 €
Engine and mechanic	90"	Iron	290	27,88%	87,00 €
		Other metals	152	14,62%	38,00 €
Body		Steel	320	30,77%	70,40 €
Windows	90"	Glass	30	2,88%	- 24,00 €
Rubber and fabrics			35	3,35%	- 4,02 €
			1.046		163,48 €
			12h 50min		

Figure 9. Dismantling results.

This action led following **data study**, looking to accomplish these performance indicators:

- i. Avoid harm
- ii. Reuse or recycle 65% of material, 95% in case 1.
- iii. Valuable material

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Electrical wiring	PVC and copper	0,96%	1.600,00 €

Figure 10. Most valuable item.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Hazardous waste: Battery, Diesel oil, Oils, Water, filters and gear oil	Lead battery, fluids and filters	1,44%	700,00 €

Figure 11. Hazardous items.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Front and rear bumpers, mudguard	PPE	4,04%	300,00 €
Radiator fan, nozzles and tanks	PA	1,15%	300,00 €
Seats	ABS	0,10%	300,00 €
Instrument panel- dashboard	PP	0,29%	300,00 €
Door panel	PP	0,48%	300,00 €
Roof	PP/ABS	0,57%	300,00 €
Engine and mechanic	Iron	27,88%	300,00 €

Figure 12. Summary of plastics found & metals not recovered automatically.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
	Other metals	14,62%	250,00 €

Figure 13. Summary of metals in very small quantities.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Body	Steel	30,77%	220,00 €

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Wheels and tires extraction	Tires	5,77%	200,00 €

Dismantling task	Main content	%	€/Ton
Windows	Glass	2,88%	- 800,00 €
Rubber and fabrics		3,35%	- 114,86 €

Figure 14. Summary items out of ECOBULK's scope.

The dismantled parts were analysed by process; defining three cases: mandatory, automatized or manual extraction with enough pureness to be sold and cross info with percentages.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	Value	Type of extraction
Hazardous waste: Battery, Diesel oil, Oils, Water, filters and gear oil	Lead battery, fluids and filters	1,44%	10,50 €	Mandatory
	Oil, gear oil, water, fuel	2,21%	- 16,10 €	Mandatory
	Filters	0,96%	- 7,00 €	Mandatory
Wheels and tires extraction	Tires	5,77%	12,00 €	Mandatory
	Rubber	3,08%	- 40,00 €	Mandatory
Parcial amount		13,46%	- 40,60 €	Mandatory

Figure 15. Mandatory parts to be removed.

Mandatory wastes are processed due to potential pollution of soil, water and air; and to awareness of misuse of some hazardous contents.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	Value	Type of extraction
Electrical wiring	PVC and copper	0,96%	16,00 €	Automatized
	Other metals	14,62%	38,00 €	Automatized
Body	Steel	30,77%	70,40 €	Automatized
Parcial amount		46,35%	124,40 €	Automatized

Figure 16. Automated removing of parts.

Automatized extraction of metals and alloys such as iron, steel, aluminium, and copper are the core business of present EoL vehicles companies.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	Value	Type of extraction
Front and rear bumpers, mudguard	PPE	4,04%	12,60 €	Manual
Radiator fan, nozzles and tanks	PA	1,15%	3,60 €	Manual
Seats	ABS	0,10%	0,30 €	Manual
Instrument panel- dashboard	PP	0,29%	0,90 €	Manual
Door panel	PP	0,48%	1,50 €	Manual
Roof	PP/ABS	0,57%	1,80 €	Manual
Engine and mechanic	Iron	27,88%	87,00 €	Manual
Windows	Glass	2,88%	- 24,00 €	Manual
Rubber and fabrics		3,35%	- 4,02 €	Manual
Parcial amount		40,74%	79,68 €	Manual

Figure 17. Remaining parts.

ECOBULK 's scope is shown on Figure 17.

Dismantling task	Main content	%	Value	Type of extraction
Electrical wiring	PVC and copper	0,96%	16,00 €	Automatized
Engine and mechanic	Iron	27,88%	87,00 €	Automatized
	Other metals	14,62%	38,00 €	Automatized
Body	Steel	30,77%	70,40 €	Automatized
Parcial amount		74,23%	211,40 €	Automatized

Figure 18. Most valuable parts at present.

There is an important percentage of LIGHT FRACTION that, at present, has no way to be competitively recycled, neither technically, nor economically.

So, taking valuable items from Figure 17 off, remaining items are summarized in Figure 19

Dismantling task	Main content	%	Value	Type of extraction
Front and rear bumpers, mudguard	PPE	4,04%	12,60 €	Manual
Radiator fan, nozzles and tanks	PA	1,15%	3,60 €	Manual
Seats	ABS	0,10%	0,30 €	Manual
Instrument panel- dashboard	PP	0,29%	0,90 €	Manual
Door panel	PP	0,48%	1,50 €	Manual
Roof	PP/ ABS	0,57%	1,80 €	Manual
Windows	Glass	2,33%	- 24,00 €	Manual
Rubber and fabrics		3,35%	- 4,02 €	Manual
Parcial amount		12,31%	- 7,32 €	Manual

Figure 19. Summary of parts to work on.

Throughout ECOBULK project these light fraction materials can be revalued and reach more than a 95% recycling level.

The core business revenues are shown on

Figure 20. In this figure is clearly exposed that only automated processes are worth for exploitation at present. So, economic considerations must be addressed in a sound analysis.

Figure 20. Present ELV revenues.

Figure 21. Percentage of revenues..

Conclusions

- Most valued material is copper because it can be recycled endlessly without losing its performance.
- Third value stream of materials is plastic.
- Its little % in one unit.
- Different families are mixed together; there is no valuable market for them.
- Its out-sorting with purity requires high investment and new technologies.
- Metals segregation is automatized and has a high performance.

If iron is not taken into account, because it is a heavy and metallic fraction, which could be automatically segregated; this remaining bulk is 12,31 % weight of the vehicle. These are the parts of the vehicle where ECOBULK project had to work on.

ECOBULK scope is quantified in % of the vehicle; main components have been identified; as well as the needs to revalue, recycle.

Figure 22. Summary of case1 scope.

Evaluation of performance indicators

Under the DoA premises (i. Avoid harm; ii. Reuse or recycle 65% of material; iii. Valuable material) a questionnaire was designed and sent to owners of demo sites or study cases.

This questionnaire was based on evaluating three main areas: economic value of each part, circular economy approach for each part and other considerations, which could be particular for each case.

It contains the good practices and lessons learnt, introduced from most of the partners, while developing ECOBULK project. See Figure 23

Figure 23. Questionnaire concept.

The questionnaire was distributed to the participants with the following format to fill in. See Figure 24.

The figure shows three overlapping questionnaire tables. The top table is titled 'ECOBULK Value Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)' and includes columns for 'PART Main parts in your prototype', 'Weight', 'Volume', 'Raw material cost', 'Production cost', and 'Comments'. The middle table is titled 'Circular economy Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)' and includes columns for 'Parts Main parts in your prototype', 'Easy to be damaged', 'Probability to be damaged', 'Reusable', 'Cost of reusing', 'Recyclable', 'Cost of recycling', and 'Comments'. The bottom table is titled 'Other Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)' and includes columns for 'Parts Main parts in your prototype', 'Labelling', 'Data base on materials', 'Easy to transport', 'Data base on applications', 'Legal barriers to reuse', 'Legal barriers to recycle', and 'Comments'. All tables have a 'Total' row at the bottom.

Figure 24. Distributed questionnaire.

Case 1 Results

Below, most outstanding results from case 1, automotive industry, can be seen.

ECOBULK		Value Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)				Comments
PART	Main parts in your prototype	Weight	Volume	Raw material cost	Production cost	
1	Switch pack	6	10	9	10	
2	Dials	8	6	8	8	
3	Buttons	7	8	8	8	
4	Fasteners	2	1	4	2	
5	Clips	1	1	2	2	
Total	5	24	26	31	30	0

(MICRO:CAB)
life without oil™

Figure 25. Microcab analysis.

Figure 26. Electric vehicles analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Most outstanding data is “production cost”, followed by “raw material cost”.
- However, “weight” and “volume” are also to be considered.
- “Switch pack” is the most relevant part. It has the highest production costs due to the combination of support, wiring, and electronics.
- Fasteners and clips play a secondary role on this approach.

ECOBULK		Value Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)				
PART	Main parts in your prototype	Weight	Volume	Raw material cost	Production cost	Comments
1	Fascia central	10	10	8	10	ABS, PC+ABS Painted
2	Dials (Screen Display)	6	6	10	8	PC Transparent
3	Air nozzles	8	8	9	9	PC+ABS in mass coloured
4	Fasteners	1	1	1	1	Steel
5	Clips	1	1	1	1	PA or POM
Total	5	26	26	29	29	5

Figure 27. Maier analysis.

Figure 28. Conventional vehicles analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Again, most outstanding data is "production cost", followed by "raw material cost".
- All indicators are balanced for each part, as this market is experienced and sound.
- There are three parts in which the indicators are high no matter which indicator is chosen.
- Facsia central is the part on which more work has been done. Its raw material cost is lower in this chart because it has been partly provided by other members of the Consortium.

Main parts in your prototype	Circular economy Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)						Comments
	Easy to be damaged	Probability to be damaged	Reusable	Cost of reusing	Recyclable	Cost of recycling	
Fascia central	5	5	5	5	10	5	Reusable only in the same model of car
Dials (Screen Display)	9	9	5	9	10	8	Reusable only in the same model of car. Disassemble of electronic devices is needed
Air nozzles	10	10	5	7	10	9	Reusable only in the same model of car
Fasteners	1	1	5	10	10	1	Reusable only in the same model of car
Clips	1	1	5	10	10	10	Reusable only in the same model of car
	5	26	26	25	41	5	33

Figure 29. Conventional vehicles analysis.

Figure 30. Conventional vehicles analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Reusable only in the same model of car.
- Disassemble of electronic devices is needed.
- The bigger the part is, it is easier to be damaged, however it has a lower cost of reusability. This is also caused because the little parts as clip and fasteners are hidden inside the assembly and therefore more protected.
- There is also a direct relation on the probability to be damaged and the quantity of surface exposed to the vehicle's users.
- All parts are 100% reusable and recyclable.
- Reusing costs are lower in bigger parts.
- Recycling costs depend on the material of which the part is made (from steel to PA or POM).

Other Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)								Comments
Main parts in your Parts prototype	Labelling	Data base on materials	Easy to transport	Data base on applications	Legal barriers to reuse	Legal barriers to recycle		
1 Fascia centra	10	10	4	10	1	1	Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the funtional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.	
2 Dials (Screen	10	10	8	10	1	1	Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the funtional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.	
3 Air nozzles	10	10	6	10	1	1	Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the funtional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.	
4 Fasteners	1	10	10	10	1	1	Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the funtional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.	
5 Clips	1	10	10	10	1	1	Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the funtional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.	
Total							5	

Figure 31. Conventional vehicles analysis.

Figure 32. Conventional vehicles analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Material selection according to material policy of the OEMs of the Automotive Sector (Panel of Homologated Materials). Design of the applications according to the functional and technical specifications from OEMs. Terms of use, maintenance, re-use and recycle at the end of life of the vehicle are included.
- Labelling depends highly on the part size. Little parts have difficulties to be labelled, such as fasteners and clips.
- Again, the bigger the part is, the higher costs of transport.
- Legal barriers to reuse or to recycle are low in every case. But they are commanded by vehicle manufacturers and security policies.
- A data base on materials properties and on materials applications is critical for a circular economy approach.

2.2. Study case 2 Furniture

Present situation

By May 2020, the Study Case 2: Furniture were yet to be installed. Due to previous delays and the Covid-19 situation, interfering to ECOBULK's project activities, therefore this demo was delayed.

Later, this task was reactivated allowing the completion of this deliverable. At present, the demo is ongoing. However, enough data and information has been collected to extract conclusions and define a dismantling protocol.

A brief summary of Study Case 2 sites is shown.

There are 4 sites where Modular Furniture by Moretti are to be tested. It has been considered that collecting information from 4 different assembling groups, and end users will enrich the experience and conclusions extracted from this furniture. A different configuration has been defined to fit functionality requested attending to activities related to each site (bedrooms, meeting rooms).

A second experience on sofas made of nonwoven materials from CNN is to be carried out by FCBA. See Figure 33

Case 2 Results

Below, most outstanding results from case 2, furniture industry, can be seen below.

ECOBULK		Value Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)				
PART	Main parts in your prototype	Weight	Volume	Raw material cost	Production cost	Comments
1	Long boards	7	5	5	6	
2	Short boards	5	3	5	6	
3	Middle boards	6	4	5	6	
4	Board connecting elements	1	1	7	1	
Total	4	19	13	22	19	0

moretticompact

Figure 35. Cosmob and MorettiCompact analysis.

Figure 36. Furniture analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- The three board sizes considered have similar results attending to any indicator.
- There is a remarking difference between boards and board connecting elements. In fact, ratio price/weight-volume-production cost is very high. Nevertheless, they play a small role within the assembly cost.

Parts	Main parts in your prototype	Circular economy Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)						Comments
		Easy to be damaged	Probability to be damaged	Reusable	Cost of reusing	Recyclable	Cost of recycling	
1	Long boards	4	4	10	2	10	7	
2	Short boards	2	2	10	2	10	7	
3	Middle boards	3	3	10	2	10	7	
4	Board connecting elements	1	1	10	2	10	7	

Figure 37. Furniture analysis.

Figure 38. Furniture analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Furniture prototypes offer a strong resistance to be damaged. This conclusion does not depend on the type of material used to make the boards or board connecting elements.
- There is a direct relation on the probability to be damaged and the quantity of surface exposed to end users.
- All parts are 100% reusable and recyclable.
- Reusing costs are smaller than recycling costs. This conclusion is very aligned to ECOBULK concept.

Parts	Main parts in your prototype	Other Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)						Comments
		Labelling	Data base on materials	Easy to transport	Data base on applications	Legal barriers to reuse	Legal barriers to recycle	
1	Long boards	10	10	7	10	10	10	
2	Short boards	10	10	9	10	10	10	
3	Middle boards	10	10	8	10	10	10	
4	Board connecting elements	5	8	10	10	10	10	

Figure 39. Furniture analysis.

Figure 40. Furniture analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- Labelling depends highly on the part size. Little parts such as board connecting elements are supplied in bags, and bags can be properly labelled.
- Legal barriers to reuse or to recycle are low in every case.
- A data base on materials properties and on materials applications is critical for a circular economy approach.

2.3. Study case 3 Building components

Present situation

At the beginning of year 2020, the University of Warwick has led the procurement process of a structural study of shelters designed by Exergy, using Ecobulk construction material. This is being done to guarantee the safe construction of the shelter in all UK demo sites. The results from this structural study presented the need to *a)* add structural reinforcements to the shelter, and *b)* perform measurements of structural integrity of the joint systems to be used. This work was conducted at the University of Warwick.

By May 2020, the Study Case 3: Building components were yet to be installed. Due to previous delays and the Covid-19 situation, interfering to ECOBULK's project activities, therefore this demo was delayed.

Later, this task was reactivated allowing the completion of this deliverable. At present, the demo is ongoing. However, enough data and information has been collected to extract conclusions and define a dismantling protocol.

A brief summary of Study Case 3 sites is shown.

There are 4 sites where these building components are to be tested: UK, Portugal, France, and Finland. A different design has been defined to fit functionality requested attending to activities related to the place, and weather conditions. See Figure 41.

Case 3 Results

Below, most outstanding results from case 3, building components, can be seen in Figure 43.

ECOBULK		Value Scales (1 the lowest to 10 the highest value)				
PART	Main parts in your prototype	Weight	Volume	Raw material cost	Production cost	Comments
1	Hollow pillars	10	9	8	8	
2	Solid planks	8	10	8	8	
3	Other componentes	7	8	8	8	
4	Fasteners	2	1	4	2	
5	Screws	1	1	2	2	
Total	5	28	29	30	28	0

Figure 43. Conenor analysis.

Figure 44. Building component analysis.

Main comments from this approach are:

- All components considered have similar results attending to any indicator.
- Big parts have more weight in all indicators.
- Indicators are balanced within each part.

Building components prototypes in demo activities have resulted to behave in a similar way to furniture components, during assembly and disassembly.

Working conditions are very different on the other hand, due to weather conditions exposure of building components prototypes. This leads to a more complex and exhaustive battery test to pass when disassembled, prior to be classified and led to reusing, repairing, or recycling.

3. Dismantling Protocols

These protocols have included following considerations:

- Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system from ITENE D6.1
- Report on collection and reverse logistics optimization from ITENE D5.1
ALL WP5 deliverables
- Quality control from IRIS, alignment with all WP6 deliverables
- Review of material and manufacturing process selection criteria from GRANTA D2.3
- Report on material conditioning processes from IRIS D3.5

3.1. Automotive protocol

3.1.1. Recycling phases

When considering a recycling operation it must be understood that the final result is totally dependent on the correct handling of a number of phases:

- 1.- Collection of worn and obsolete applications.
- 2.- Disassembling and removal of non-compatible materials.
- 3.- Sorting of different resins and grades.
- 4.- Washing and grinding.
- 5.- Quality checking, upgrading.
- 6.- Conversion into quality-consistent material.

Figure 45. Recycling phases demo 1.

3.1.2. Economic recycling

Recycling must have a defined objective, central to which will be the establishment of the quickest, simplest and lowest cost method of reclaiming useful and processable plastic materials. The principal economic element in this procedure is the time factor in combination with labour costs, particularly in respect of gathering, disassembling and sorting operations. Key is the application being designed using a combination of compatible materials. The following factors will have a positive influence on the economic viability of recycling:

- Fast and logical gathering.
- Fast disassembly.
- Non-labour-intensive sorting.
- No cost or low-cost cleaning procedures.
- Increasing costs for deposition and incineration.

3.1.3. Relationship of product lifetime-recycling period

To analyse when and where the bulk of recyclable material can be expected to come from, it is useful to make an estimation of the average real lifetime of a range of applications and, therefore, the timeframe in which they will be disposed of.

3.1.4. Production / Recycling material flow-scheme

Design for recycling is essential if material is to continuously flow back through the system to fulfil further manufacturing needs. However, this can only be realised when everyone involved in the design and development of a new product, is fully aware of recycling principles and requirements. The choice of basic materials, appropriate design techniques and the optimal processing of

a resin, all determine the final result of the recycling process, technically and in economic terms.

3.1.5. Design for recycling

One of the main factors determining environmental responsible products is the capability of reusing its components in whatever form possible thereby reducing waste streams. A broader perspective is required in areas like:

- Residual functional and economical value of the materials and components with which he designs.
- Easy disassembling including the separation of non-compatible materials.
- Rapid safe sorting methods.
- Cleaning operations.
- Economics and form of preparation for reuse.
- Logistics of materials retrieval systems and possible interactions with other systems.

3.1.6. Design for easy disassembling

Design for disassembly is a key action within the “recycle friendly product” development phase, as optimal adaption of products will lead to:

- Easier material and component sorting.
- Reduced handling and labour.
- Improved overall economics.
- Waste reduction.

As paradoxical as it may seem to develop a product that is assembled to be easily disassembled, it requires an enlargement of perspective relative to traditional product design and engineering rather than a complete refocus on design methods.

3.1.7. Integration

Essentially one must strive for the highest degree of component consolidation technically possible, up to the limit where functionality requires different components. Using the possibilities offered by plastics for maximum integration, through their ability to form complicated parts, may lead to substantial reduction in part count and material mix or incompatible material combinations. Subsequent, positive effects will extend beyond the economy of assembly operations alone and result in improved disassembly operations, material recovery and related economics. Translating separate functional components into one main multi-functional part requires an “open minded” approach as radical redesign is often necessary.

3.1.8. Fixing systems

Disassembling has to be realised with the minimum possible effort in every aspect. Speed and simplicity are key and are dominated by fastening methods, using their careful selection in the design phase. Within the selection criteria, automated disassembly should be considered as it typically also allows easy manual disassembly and facilitates future developments. Design in engineering plastics allows for the use of “push, hook and click” assembling techniques that are easily disassembled manually, with the aid of simple tools, or automatically.

Use of metal clamps, screws, inserts and other non-compatible assembly items should be avoided although this is not always possible. If applied, it is critical that these items are magnetic and easily accessible to facilitate ease of separation in any method applicable. Ideally fixings and fasteners should be designed in compatible materials whenever this is practicable.

3.1.9. Predetermined break areas

Good practice is to design in such a way that interconnection points and joints are easily accessible for opening, loosening or separating non-compatible items by hand. Either with simple tools or automated systems. In those cases where irreversible “once-locked-never-to-open” connections or inserted non-compatible items are applied, “predetermined break areas” can be designed-in. These can also prevent “unauthorised” second use as the parts become irreparable after disconnecting.

3.1.10. Product layout

In “design for easy assembling” attention to the way products are laid-out is seen as one of the key focal points for successful rationalisation of assembling. Product layout also has great influence on the ease of disassembling, with subsequent positive effect on costs, making the need for its intensive study in the design phase even greater.

In general, the route is to design products allowing simple actions in assembling avoiding complex manipulation of parts, components, fasteners and modules thus, in reverse, leading to optimised disassembly. To accomplish this often requires a radical redesign of products into easily accessible building blocks or modules, which allows stacked or vertical products build-up with a minimum of manipulation. Typically, the modules are a chassis of some form acting as a carrier for additional components to be “dropped-in”. This “module” or “chassis” approach, from the design for easy assembly” guidelines, can be applied in conjunction with those given for “design for disassembly”.

3.1.11. Material mix reduction

It is common practice, for economic reasons, to use lower grade cost materials for less critical parts. However, the use of non-compatible materials may result in difficulty if not the impossibility of recycling, leading to possible cost penalties. The goal of material selection should be to reduce or even eliminate the need for the disassembly of a product in total by utilising compatible resins. Although not always realistic for all products, it can however be achieved more easily for sub-assemblies within them. The strategy is to match all materials with the parts requiring higher performance characteristics. This “over-designing” will increase the initial cost of the product but may have an improved overall life cycle economy compared with traditional designs.

3.1.12. Welding

The use of welding techniques is well-known in the plastics industry, and the various systems available provide ample possibilities to join parts into a complete component. Although irreversible, thermal techniques like hot-plate, hot-gas, spin, vibration and ultrasonic welding in most cases involve compatible materials therefore separation may not be required at all. With heat-staking, separation by breaking is often inevitable but as the connections are relatively weak it may, although not ideal, be applied.

3.1.13. Adhesive bonding/cementing techniques

If the previously mentioned techniques for joining plastic parts together cannot be used because of irregular joint shapes, bonding or cementing techniques are a frequent alternative. Solvent cementing techniques currently have an advantage, with respect to recycling, over bonding with secondary materials because the latter can cause heavy contamination or result in more complicated disassembling. However, when utilizing solvent bonding strict measures have to be taken to prevent solvents entering the environment.

Basically, only amorphous materials can be solvent cemented because of their solubility in certain solvents. With semi-crystalline materials it may be necessary to use adhesives techniques because of their inert chemical behaviour. When use of adhesives is unavoidable, it is advised to research the use of compatible adhesives, to ensure that material properties are not adversely affected.

3.1.14. Secondary operations

Apart from the cleaning of dust and any adhering dirt, which can be done by washing or high pressure cleaning, it is important to remove materials used for colouring, decoration and information such as paints, metal plating, hot-foil prints and stamped on textiles, etc. These operations are in many cases necessary to prevent material contamination thereby increasing of cost and complexity of the retrieval operations.

For aesthetic purposes it is common to use paints, foils, etc. also environmental protective paints and coatings may be required. Most of these secondary finishes need to be removed unless they exhibit relatively low material deterioration effects due to compatibility or to low concentrations. Although advanced paint removal techniques are being developed, it is advisable to avoid painting and use the possibilities of “colouring-in” techniques, provided by plastics. Where special accents or shadow effects are desired in-moulded textures, reliefs and advanced ink diffusion techniques can be an alternative.

From a recycling point of view, metal plating of plastics can be considered a hurdle. Advanced removal systems utilizing mechanical, electro-chemical and ultrasonic cleaning techniques are being developed with high priority in conjunction with industry and these will provide a benefit for the future.

Decorations or instructions are often presented by means of adhesive labels, hot-foil prints, etc. Depending on the type of adhesive it is generally possible to remove these non-compatible labelling systems by chemical or mechanical methods. Less costly is the use of adhesives which are water soluble which is especially applicable for reusable items like bottles. Alternatively, one may use “pop-in-pop-out” labelling which can be separated more easily or moulded-in reliefs and which are particularly applicable for instructions on equipment.

3.1.15. Design for rapid, safe sorting

To be assured of perfect batches of material for recycling it is necessary to be able to easily sort the plastic parts after gathering and disassembling. Different methods can be applied and are already used by manufacturers to identify and distinguish the plastic parts and the material they are composed of. A system for material identification should be thoroughly considered before it is adopted, as any subsequent change in methods will cause disruption to sorting facilities. A number of identification methods are presented here, ranked most to least preferred.

In-mould coding. This method of material identification should always be used as it not only allows easy sorting but also provides the possibilities of adding specific material descriptions. The codes of symbols, designating the resin used, could follow standards such as VDA 260/DIN 6120/ ISO 1043/ SAE 1344. These should be engraved in the mould and reproduced on a non-appearance surface of the product but still easily readable.

Bar coding. This method is currently under development and may eventually lead to a system for fully-automated part and material sorting. The information is added to the parts via in-moulding in the form of a relief or via laser-marking techniques currently being developed. The resultant bar code information can be read by machine.

Colour coding. Colour coding can be realised by having within one assembly, all parts made from the same resin or grade in an identical colour. This method is only relevant for on product recycling stream as it is not fool-proof when interaction exists with other relative non-controllable ones. It should be considered an additional aid in sorting rather than an identification system.

3.1.16. ECOBULK Automotive Demonstrators

The three automotive demonstrators (FIAT, MAIER, MicroCab) are currently ongoing to fulfil the following objectives:

- Validation of manufactured and (re-)manufactured products.
- Demonstration of design considerations: modularity and product/part reuse/recovery/recycle.
- Evaluation of assembly/upgrade processes to ensure robustness and repeatability.
- Validation of the upgrade/refurbishment processes.
- Integration of new modules/functionalities and customization/personalization.
- Upgrade of disassembly/dismantling processes by using new connections and fasteners.
- Validation of disassembling/dismantling process vs current practices.

ECOBULK Fascia. Description of the component (MAIER)

The ECOBULK Fascia developed by MAIER as functional prototype is a component that includes different parts made of injected plastic, joined to the cockpit with standard snap fits moulded on back of the parts. The electric+electronic devices (audio, video, GPS, etc.) are fixed with a metallic frame to the fascia and cockpit by standard fasteners (steel screws and nuts). The design of the ECOBULK Fascia is based on commercial versions of similar applications currently produced by MAIER. This prototype fascia has been re-designed to be injected by a 2K moulding process. The front side of the part is made of a conventional plastic material to obtain the high quality aesthetic functionality. The back side includes the same structural functionalities than the commercial version. A number of ECOBULK materials (bioplastics, recycled) has been injected on this back side to evaluate the performance of the ECOBULK Fascia compared to the commercial versions. As those ECOBULK materials are fully compatible to the plastic injected on the front side of the part, there is no need to dismantle and recycle separately the aesthetic and structural elements of the application.

Figure 46. Fascia – Central Console. Commercial version (left) and ECOBULK prototype (right)

Figure 47. ECOBULK Fascia. Front Side (Aesthetic)

Figure 48. ECOBULK Fascia. Back Side (Structural)

Figure 49. ECOBULK Fascia. Video Display Screen Assembly

Figure 50. ECOBULK Fascia. Air Conditioning Vents Assembly

The following pictures show the steps of the process needed to dismantle a fascia (commercial version produced by MAIER), starting from the initial configuration (functional vehicle). The design of the fixation system has been optimized to help a normal person (owner of the vehicle) to follow the whole process of dismantling/assembly in a few minutes, by using the hands and a standard screwdriver. This “easy-to-do” method allows both the maintenance operations (substitution of damaged elements, update of electric+electronic devices) and the dismantling at the End of Life of the vehicle.

The design of the functional prototype ECOBULK Fascia has been done in the same way than the commercial version, to fulfil the technical specifications

regarding the assembly/dismantling of each of the individual parts of the cockpit.

Figure 51. Step #1. Fascia+ Air Conditioning Vents+ Dashboard Lower Trim

Figure 52. Step #2. Dashboard Lower Trim

Figure 53. Step #3. Audio System Display+Frame

Figure 54. Step #4. Electrical+Electronic Devices

Once this part is disassembled, next process is shredding into new pellets, an adding a percentage of these to the new raw material.

Figure 55. Case 1 within Ecobulk concept.

A chart describing Bellver' tasks in this activity are found below:

Figure 56. Shredding process.

Figure 57. Shredding process visualisation.

3.2. Furniture protocol

This section addresses a dismantling protocol for the furniture prototypes of demo 2 in a circular economy framework.

Figure 58. Recycling phases demo 2.

* Reuse, repair, recycle

Description

Collection of worn and rejected furniture

Collect information of material, size, conditions, and number of pieces of furniture. Determine transport and tools needed according to type of anchors, screws, and possible tools that will be required to disassemble the furniture.

Disassembling and into smaller parts materials

Do all disassembly in one go. It is preferable not to interrupt the disassembly process, nor the assembly process. Otherwise junctures can be over stressed and be damaged.

Collet screws, nuts, washers and small parts in bags and tag them. Store them in separate bags and write down which piece it is and how many are in each container.

Wrap bigger parts appropriately and tag them.

Number the parts and bulks.

First quality checking and classification according RRR*.

Check damage and state of each part, from a structural and a furnishing point of view.

Classify in three bulk depending the first work to be don on the part: reuse, repair, recycle. Write down how many pieces and what format each one is, as

well as its position in the fixtures. This will help to check in a further inspection the possible upgrading that has to be done.

Transport and store each bulk in an appropriate environment, considering the best practice for each type of material and its value.

Sort parts according to classification

Each bulk must go to a second and formal quality control made by specialised workshops.

Formal quality checking, upgrading

Previous analysis has led to the conclusion in furniture industry, that repairing, and reusing is the best option, whenever it is feasible.

Repairing damaged parts ensures that they will meet customers' criteria and will be able to be introduced in the manufacturing chain again. Repairs consume far fewer resources and reduces carbon footprint.

Too damaged parts should be recycled.

Integration in a new piece of furniture

Design and technical department will study and develop the best way to integrate these renewed parts into new or different pieces of furniture, as its modular and compact original design will contribute.

Figure 59. New pieces of furniture to be manufactured.

3.3. Construction protocol

This section addresses a dismantling protocol for the furniture prototypes of demo 2 in a circular economy framework.

Figure 60. Recycling phases demo 3.

* Reuse, repair, recycle

Description

Collection of worn and rejected building components

Collect information of material, size, conditions, and number of pieces of building components. Determine transport and tools needed according to type of anchors, screws, and possible tools that will be required to disassemble the building components.

Disassembling and into smaller parts materials

Do all disassembly in one go. It is preferable not to interrupt the disassembly process, nor the assembly process. Otherwise junctures can be over stressed and be damaged.

Collet screws, nuts, washers and small parts in bags and tag them. Store them in separate bags and write down which piece it is and how many are in each container.

Wrap bigger parts appropriately and tag them.

Number the parts and bulks.

First quality checking and classification according RRR*.

Check damage and state of each part, from a structural and a furnishing point of view.

Classify in three bulk depending the first work to be don on the part: reuse, repair, recycle. Write down how many pieces and what format each one is, as

well as its position in the fixtures. This will help to check in a further inspection the possible upgrading that has to be done.

Transport and store each bulk in an appropriate environment, considering the best practice for each type of material and its value.

Sort parts according to classification

Each bulk must go to a second and formal quality control made by specialised workshops.

Formal quality checking, upgrading

Previous analysis has led to the conclusion in construction of building components, that repairing, and reusing is the best option, whenever it is feasible.

Repairing damaged parts ensures that they will meet customers' criteria and will be able to be introduced in the manufacturing chain again. Repairs consume far fewer resources and reduces carbon footprint.

Too damaged parts should be recycled.

Integration in a new piece of building components

Design and technical department will study and develop the best way to integrate these repaired and reworked parts into brand new building components.

Figure 61. New building components to manufacture.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

4.1 EC Policies. Circular Economy

4.1.1. Overview

Managing the life cycle of natural resources, from extraction through the design and manufacture of products, to what is considered as waste is essential to green growth and part of developing a resource-efficient, circular economy where nothing is wasted. Smarter design allowing products to be repaired, re-used, remanufactured and then recycled again should become the norm.

It's good for business, citizens and nature. The European Commission promotes resource efficiency, encourages eco-innovation, provides tools that can help you recognize green products and supports eco-friendly, innovative businesses.

A greener economy means new growth and job opportunities. Eco-design, eco-innovation, waste prevention and the reuse of raw materials can bring net savings for EU businesses of up to EUR 600 billion. Additional measures to increase resource productivity by 30 % by 2030 could boost GDP by nearly 1 %, while creating 2 million additional jobs. It also benefits the environment and reduces Europe's greenhouse gas emissions.

The [Europe 2020 Strategy](#) is the Commission's strategy for smart, inclusive and sustainable growth. The Commission actively supports businesses, administrations and consumers so that together, **we can turn the Union into**

a resource-efficient, green, and competitive low-carbon economy. This is one of the three objectives of the [7th Environment Action Programme](#). To get growing again and create new jobs, while contributing to the global [Sustainable Development Goals](#), Europe cannot afford to waste this opportunity.

[Circular Economy Package](#): The Commission has adopted a package of measures and legislative proposals to boost sustainable growth and help Europe make the transition towards a more circular economy.

4.1.2. EU Circular Economy Action Plan,

A new Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe. The European Commission has adopted a new [Circular Economy Action Plan](#) - one of the main blocks of the [European Green Deal](#), Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth.

The new Action Plan announces initiatives along the entire life cycle of products, targeting for example their design, promoting circular economy processes, fostering sustainable consumption, and aiming to ensure that the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible.

It introduces legislative and non-legislative measures targeting areas where action at the EU level brings real added value.

4.1.3. Actions

The new Circular Economy Action presents measures to:

- Make sustainable products the norm in the EU;
- Empower consumers and public buyers;
- Focus on the sectors that use most resources and where the potential for circularity is high such as: electronics and ICT; batteries and vehicles; packaging; plastics; textiles; construction and buildings; food; water and nutrients;
- Ensure less waste;
- Make circularity work for people, regions and cities,
- Lead global efforts on circular economy.

4.1.4. Key documents

- [Communication: A new Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe](#) - [publication](#) - [press release](#) - [questions and answers](#) - [factsheet](#)
- [Communication: A new Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More Competitive Europe](#) - [annex](#)
- [Implementation tracking table](#)
- [Staff working document 'Leading the way to a global circular economy: state of play and outlook'](#)

4.2. Automotive plastic trends

It is currently more difficult to introduce new materials into the automotive industry than was previously the case². Suppliers are looking for cost-efficient methods, while new materials frequently call for new machines and other investments in the production process.

Plastics are raising challenges as well. In addition to competing as an often less expensive alternative to steel and aluminium, and as a constantly developing material, plastics are affected by volatile oil prices and variable production volumes. Because of these factors, the market is characterised by considerable uncertainty.

Despite these global obstacles, the many advantages of plastics have earned them a place in the automotive market. The sustainability and performance characteristics of fibre-reinforced plastics are particularly attractive to European car manufacturers. Although it may seem contradictory, plastics also have an environmentally friendly aspect: thermoplastics.

Environmental trends

One of the most prominent trends in the automotive industry involves making vehicles lighter, thereby reducing their emissions. Heavy-weight steel parts are being replaced by lightweight composites, carbon fibre, glass fibre and other plastics. Although the source is not renewable, the production process itself is more efficient in terms of energy, as compared to steel.

² *CBI Product Factsheet: Plastics for vehicles in the European Union.*

Recycling is another issue in the automotive industry. Despite the industry's excellent record in the area of recycling, reuse and recycling are presenting challenges in the use of all thermoset plastics. In particular, European regulations require a high rate of re-use and recycling for each vehicle. Importers are therefore likely to exercise considerable caution when importing thermoset plastics.

Trends involving quality

Simply recycling plastics reduces the purity and performance of the material. In recent years, however, fibre-reinforced plastics have been introduced, combining the material characteristics and cost-competitiveness of steel with the recyclability and lightweight characteristics of plastics. For example, natural-fibre composites are currently being used for interior door trims. Wood-plastic composites are used for the rear shelf, as well as for the trunk and spare wheel trims.

Roof liners and dashboards are often made of fibreglass-reinforced composites. Pure plastic is used for interior door trim, pillars and trunks. In addition to their sustainability features, fibre-reinforced plastics offer advantages with regard to performance.

Developments in the crash performance and resistance of plastics have made safety an area in which considerable progress could be achieved. In addition, the flexibility of the material is quite welcome in terms of aesthetics, while its stiffness makes plastics suitable for optimising long-term passenger comfort.

Future market developments for natural-fibre reinforced composites remain difficult to predict, as estimates vary widely.

Nevertheless, natural-fibre composites have clearly become an integral part of the industry, and they continue to develop in terms of strength, crash performance and stiffness, while remaining light in weight.

4.3. New strategies to implement

An overview of conclusions applicable to all sectors studied on ECOBULK's project, can be summarized in 6 key areas that are undergoing a massive transformation in the waste management industry³.

1. Improved Recycling Rates

Recycling and waste management companies are investing in improving their tools and techniques. The recent development in single-stream recycling where people can dump all the trash in one bin has reduced the sorting burden on people and drastically improved the rate of recycling. This has also reduced the truck count and ultimately the emissions as well.

2. Automated Waste Collection

Technology has transformed the way waste management works with automated sensors that trigger instant alerts every time a container is full and needs service. Other innovative tools that are making the sorting process fast and easy include optical sorters, magnets and advanced disk screens. The trucks have also switched from diesel to natural gas for quieter and cost-effective operations. The use of logistics software, in-vehicle monitors, and mobile apps has further simplified the waste management process while ensuring driver safety.

³ *Compactor Management Company*

3. Route Optimization

Optimal routing is essential to protecting the environment and reducing hazardous emissions which is why companies are investing in advanced systems and optimization software. They are now employing automated trucks that are installed with robotic arms for saving time and effort along existing routes. Technology has made point-to-point pickups eco-friendly and financially viable while improving energy-efficiency.

4. Landfill Modernization

Harnessing the power of science and scale, the waste management industry has modernized garbage dumps. Highly engineered landfills that comply with federal and state regulations ensure complete protection of human health and the surrounding environment. Solar panel systems integrated with geomembrane are facilitating the production of sustainable energy while preventing carbon from re-entering the environment.

5. Enhanced Safety

Recycling and waste management companies are making consistent efforts to improve safety which is of prime importance to an industry running several 30-ton trucks through residential areas. All of their drivers are subjected to rigorous training at designated facilities to reduce the rate of accidents and injuries.

6. Quick Turnaround Times

Bigger waste management companies have also invested in feature-rich customer-facing technology. They are leveraging user-friendly mobile apps to facilitate prompt service, extra pickups and bill payment through push notifications. Technology has greatly reduced the complexity and cost of modern-day waste management systems making them all the more efficient, safer and productive while reducing their environmental impact.

Figure 62. Strategies to implement.

4.4. Automotive sector conclusions

The recycling of plastics has thus become a hotly discussed and sometimes controversial subject of political, industrial and public debate. To work out solutions that will be acceptable to all sides, however, requires an objective look at the options and limitations of plastics recycling.

The legislation on the recycling of scrap vehicles will require manufacturers and retailers to reclaim vehicles and recycle their component materials. The aim is to carefully disassemble scrap vehicles and thereby pinpoint means of recycling the used plastics components. A key prerequisite for high-grade recycling is a marking system for identifying and sorting the different types of plastics used in vehicle components.

This work is aimed at finding secondary applications for quality-assured recycled plastics, primarily in the sector in which they were used, in this case the automotive industry. In addition to this, other efforts are focusing on logistics and the preparations for recycling, such as identification, coating removal and stabilisation.

The intensive efforts that have gone into the recycling of plastic automotive components show that single-sort plastics components can be readily recycled. However, for logistical reasons (identification, sorting) and on economic grounds (dismantling intensity, preparation into single-sort regrind), only selected parts should be dismantled. The other components remain in the car body and make up the shredder fluff which emerges after shredding.

Apart from the aspects of technical feasibility, which have been the main aspects considered here, there are also economic and ecological aspects to be borne in mind. We cannot opt for recycling if the costs are too high. The percentage of plastics products that cannot be re-used must be drastically reduced. The experience and findings that we gain in the material recycling of plastics (including those cases where material recycling is not yet economically viable) thus represent a fundamental prerequisite for the development of materials, processes and products for the future which are optimised in recycling terms.

It is not uncommon for incompatible plastics to be combined in automotive components, and many cases completely different materials are used for the same components of different models in one and the same range. In addition, accessories and spare parts were often moulded in different materials again. This intermingling of grades is currently presenting many problems in the material recycling of plastics from scarp cars.

The current practice of marking materials according to type, the automated plastics identification and sorting methods which are at present under development, and additional separation methods will help to make the task of recycling plastic components much easier.

Efficient assembly techniques are an essential feature of cost-effective component design. Apart from component assembly, consideration must also be given at the design stage to cost-efficient dismantling.

The dismantling operation is not simply the assembly operation in reverse. Different constraints prevail during dismantling. Consideration can also be given to dismantling techniques which destroy the component. A large number of dismantling tests, however, have revealed destructive techniques to be generally less efficient than selective dismantling.

Snap joints that are readily accessible and can easily be undone with standard tools not only offer enormous advantages when it comes to repairs but are also ideal for subsequent dismantling.

One important factor is that persons who are not familiar with the unit in question should be able to readily identify the possibilities it offers for dismantling.

4.5. Furniture sector conclusions

Results from the furniture demos:

- The standard and modular components manufactured by Moretti Compact allowed for the construction of the furniture in the office spaces at the University of Warwick to be achieved without major issues.
- The user experience assessments will inform the demo activities about the user needs and acceptance of the furniture products.
- The demonstration site will likely raise users' awareness of circularity in the furniture sector.
- Based on the modular design proposed by Moretti and the assemble instructions, the assemble/disassemble exercises in the furniture products is expected to be completed without delays or major issues.

The correct dismantling of furniture products is fundamental for virtually every stage of products within a circular model (maintain, repair, reuse, refurbish, repurpose, and recycle). From a technical and economical perspective, this industry sector has the opportunity to move towards achieving the following goals in the next 5 to 10 years.

- **Increase in quality:** higher quality materials, away from current cheaper alternatives, can allow efficient dismantling without comprising the potential of parts to be repaired or refurbished to be reused or

upgraded. Higher quality of materials will be required in the near future such that producers and customers have the confidence to dismantle for repair and reuse.

- **Moving away from using hazardous chemicals:** a significant obstacle for the dismantling of furniture, particularly with purposes of repair and recycling, is the use of hazardous chemicals in wood binders, glues, dyes, stains, and paints. As products are dismantled, the exposure of personnel to some of these substances can be harmful, raising safety concerns in activities of refurbishing and repurposing. Therefore, the reduction, elimination, or replacement of hazardous chemicals will continue to be relevant for the circularity of furniture in the next 5 to 10 years.
- **Decreasing added cost from dismantling and reclaiming:** the reclaiming process will likely present an additional cost to reclaimed, recycled, and reused products. The reduction of the cost of reclaimed products, either through incentives from governments or the distribution of costs between user throughout the life of a product can help decreasing these costs.

4.6. Construction sector conclusions

Results from construction demos:

- Some requirements and barriers for the deployment and use of circular construction materials were identified. For instance, some of the partners required the procurement of structural studies on the structures designed with the circular construction materials for the construction of the demos. This was done to guarantee the safety of the structures. In addition, the structural properties of the materials and their behavior under different weather conditions are partially studied. This makes challenging to accurately predict the structural integrity of component at the end of cycle of product life, prior disassembly. Further research is required.
- The lifetime of the construction demos will affect some of decisions made around joint systems, foundations, and anchoring of the shelters. For instance, short-term structures may be supported on post-spike support, whereas mid-term structures would require a flat slab on ground, depending on the terrain. This will ultimately affect the dismantling protocols and, for the time being, this may be considered on a case-by-case basis.
- The user experience assessments will inform the demo activities about the user needs and acceptance of the construction products. The constructors are found to be a relevant stakeholder, to be considered in future consultations.

- The demonstration site will likely raise users' awareness of circularity in the furniture sector.

The dismantling of products and components in the construction sector will face the following opportunities in the next 5 to 10 years.

- **Standardization:** Given the construction sector utilizes a wide range of providers, manufacturers, and constructors, all with different specialties, the standardization of processes and components across all this sector will be required for the widespread application of dismantling.
- **Non-destructive testing (NDT):** A clear prerequisite for the dismantling of construction structures is to guarantee that these are safe for operators and future life stages of a component (eg. reuse). NDT technologies can guarantee that structural components are safe for dismantling, instead of demolition for disposal.
- **Safety assessments:** The exposure of dismantling personnel to compromised structures represents a major challenge for the construction sector. Technical risks assessments and measures to reduce the risk of personnel are needed.

5. References

The following bibliography has been used in this deliverable.

5.1 General references

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- Deliverable 2,4 Report on Design Circular framework setting ITENE
- Deliverable 2,6 Prototypes TU DELFT
- Deliverable 4,4 Demonstration plans for activities at DEMO SITES: User involvement CONENOR
- Deliverable 5,1 Report on collection and reverse logistics optimization. ITENE
- Deliverable 5,3 Solutions for the final sorting of Bulky Waste TOMRA
- Deliverable 5,4 Solutions of the final sorting of End-of-Life Vehicle Shredder Light Fraction. AIMPLAS
- Deliverable 5,5 Characterization and Selection of materials from MBW and ELV for recycling. CNR
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